

ACOUSTICAL SPECTROSCOPY OF POLYMERIC MATRICES

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ABSTRACT

It was considered some possibilities of the acoustical spectroscopy of polymeric matrices. Among them: investigation of relaxation processes by analysis of temperature dependence of the velocity elastic waves $C = f(T)$; new method of the determination of activation energy which is applied even by measurement on one frequency; determination of the density network ν . It was considered also the new experimental facts obtained by using the acoustic methods. It is showed that in the main relaxation region many polymeric matrices have double temperature transition. It is studied the influence of density network on the magnitude of storage modulus G' about and below T_g . It was established that at $T < T_g$ G' dependet anomalously on ν . For analysis was used the results of experimental investigation of series epoxy resins in temperature interval from 77 to 470 K at frequencies 0,2 and 2 Hz.

INTRODUCTION

Acoustic methods of investigating polymers applied wide. The basic traditional parameters which are studied by this are components of the complex modulus of elasticity: the dynamic modulus, loss modulus and loss tangent. At the same time assume ever greater importance the study of temrerature dependence of elastic waves velocity and absorbtion coefficient [1].

The dynamic viscoelastic properties of polymeric matrices are studied by using the lowfrequencies elastic vibrations. These properties are examined as the lowfrequencies acoustical properties. It is interesting that in this case it is easy to determine the velocity of elastic waves. For example by using the method of free torsional oscillations it can be determined both dynamic shear modulus G' and low-frequency velocity of shear waves

$$C_t = \sqrt{\frac{G'}{\rho}} \quad (1)$$

where the ρ is density of polymer.

The parameters characterizing the dynamic viscoelastic properties of polymers are mainly governed by two factors: the chemical structure and the specific features of the

supermolecular structure. There exist a clear-cut correlation between chemical structure, physical structure, molecular mobility and acoustic parameters of polymers. The values and the mode of variation of these parameters with temperature are determined by the bond energy of the main-chain atoms and the interaction energy of the units of neighbouring polymeric chains, i.e., the intermolecular interaction energy. In this paper I want to show the new possibilities of the acoustical spectroscopy by analyses temperature dependence the velocity of elastic waves. As objects of investigation were selected epoxide polymers.

TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF THE VELOCITY OF ELASTIC WAVES IN EPOXIDE POLYMERS.

It is known that the molecular mobility and connected with it the relaxation processes determine the wide complex of the physical properties of polymers. Usually about the molecular mobility and corresponding to that the relaxation processes judge by maximums

Figure 1.

Temperature dependence of elastic waves velocity C and $\tan \delta$ for single relaxation process.

on the temperature dependence of $\tan \delta$ or loss modulus G'' . Less traditional but more informativ is the investigation of relaxation processes in amorphous polymers by analysis of the temperature dependence of velocity elastic waves $C = f(T)$. This way is based on the fact that the velocity of elastic waves depends linearly on the temperature and only when the nature of molecular mobility changes a jump is observed on the curve of the temperature coefficient of the velocity of elastic waves. This is observed as temperature transition on the

dependence C plots T [1, 2]. Numerous experimental facts displayed that temperature dependence of velocity of the elastic waves near some temperature transition T_0 can describe by following empiric formula

$$C = C_0[1 - \delta_i(T - T_0)] \quad (2)$$

where $\delta = \frac{1}{C} \cdot \frac{\Delta C}{\Delta T}$ - temperature coefficient of velocity of elastic waves, $i = 1$ or 2 ; δ_1 correspond to $T < T_0$ and δ_2 for $T > T_0$; C_0 - velocity of elastic waves at T_0 . The typical

Figure 2.

Temperature dependences C_i and $\tan \delta$ near glass transition in cured epoxide resin ED - 20 .

diagram of the temperature transitions obtained in polymers including the polymer matrices on the graphs $C = f(T)$ and $\tan\delta = f(T)$ for single relaxation process is showed on the figure 1.

Usually it is supposed that at T_1 begin to defreeze some kind of the molecular mobility which is the reason of this relaxation process, but T'_1 is the highly temperature boundary of this process.

For glass transition T_1 is usually good corresponded (at measuring on the low frequencies coincide) with the glass transition temperature T_g . Usually is very important to know the temperature T_1 by which unfreeze some kind of the molecular motion.

At $T \leq T_1$ the relaxation times of almost all relaxation processes are very large and for them the condition $\omega_1\tau_1 = N_1 \gg 1$ is fulfilled. High-temperature boundary of this relaxation process is $T = T'_1$ (on the C_T plots T). For this the condition $\omega_2\tau_2 = N_2 \ll 1$ is fulfilled.

It is interesting that the magnitudes of the temperature coefficient of the velocity of elastic waves below and above T_0 can differ. In full measure it become apparent near T_g . Below T_g the quantity of $\Delta C / \Delta T$ is few $m \cdot s^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$, but above T_g is scores $m \cdot s^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$. According to it $\delta_2 / \delta_1 = 3 \div 10$.

For the analyses we used the results of our investigations of the cross-linked epoxide polymers. These polymers were studied by using the automatic inverted torsion pendulum in temperature region $77 \div 470K$ at frequencies 0,2 and 2 Hz. The shear storage modulus G' , loss tangent $\tan\delta$ and velocity of low-frequency shear elastic waves $C_t = \sqrt{\frac{G'}{\rho}}$ (where ρ - density of polymer) were measured with inaccuracies in G' , $\tan\delta$ and C_t from 2 to 4%, 5 to 6% and 1 to 2% respectively. It was established that at $T > T_g$ all investigated epoxide polymers [1,3] have δ_2 approximately equal $\delta \approx 3,5 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot K^{-1}$.

The determination of the temperatures T_1 and T'_1 allows determine the interval of the temperatures $\Delta T = T'_1 - T_1$ in which display the relaxation process and find the activation energy of this process [4]. Really supposing that the relaxation time τ followed to the Arrhenius equation it's easy to observe that

$$\frac{N_1}{N_2} = \frac{\omega_1\tau_1}{\omega_2\tau_2} = \frac{\omega_1}{\omega_2} \exp \frac{U\Delta T}{RT'_1T_1} \quad (3)$$

Here ω_1 and ω_2 are the acoustic oscillation frequencies which correspond to temperatures T_1 and T'_1 , R - universal gas constant. Using Eqn.(3) we get for activation energy of the relaxation process

$$U = AR \frac{T'_1T_1}{\Delta T} \quad (4)$$

where $A = \ln(\tau_1 / \tau_2)$. Here τ_1 and τ_2 are the relaxation times at temperatures T_1 and T_1' . For glass transition (α relaxation) is $A_\alpha = 14$ for amorphous polymers of the every chemical structure. For process β - relaxation is $A_\beta = 8,5$. The application of the above stated possibilities based on the using of the dependences $C = f(T)$ for the study of the epoxide matrices allow to establish the series of important features of the viscoelastic behavior of this polymer class.

On the dependence $C_i = f(T)$ (fig.2) in the glass transition region were obtained two temperature transitions. Earlier was established [1, 2, 5] that the linear amorphous polymers in glass transition region have two temperature transition. T_0 the transition with low temperature T_2 correspond the unfreezing of segmental motion in the unordered matrix, and to the more high-temperature transition at $T_1 = T_g$ correspond the unfreezing of segmental mobility inside the more ordered regions-inside the anticrystalline clusters [1, 5]. Epoxy-phenolic matrix has $T_2 = 352K$ and $T_1 = T_g = 360K$. Transitions $T_2' = 367K$ and $T_1' = 381K$ are high-temperatures boundaries of α -relaxation. Some epoxide matrices have in glass transition region double α -peak of $\tan \delta$ [2].

ACOUSTIC PROPERTIES AND SPACE NETWORK DENSITY.

It is known that the expression for dynamic shear modulus of cross-linked polymers can be written as

Figure 3.

Temperature dependence of dynamic Young's modulus E' (1,2,3) for three epoxide resins having a different space network density: 1 - ED - 20; 2 - ED - 16; 3 - EDL.

$$G' = G_0 + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{H(\tau) \omega^2 \tau^2}{1 + \omega^2 \tau^2} d(\ln \tau) \quad (5)$$

where $H(\tau)$ is the density of the spectrum of relaxation times,

$$G_0 = \nu RT \quad (6)$$

Here G_0 is the equilibrium shear modulus, $\nu = \rho / M_c$ - polymer network density, ρ - density of polymers, M_c - molecular mass of a section of a polymer chain between two cross-links. In the region of the rubberlike-plateau, all the relaxation times τ_j making the main contribution to the relaxation spectrum are small, and the condition that $\omega \tau_j \ll 1$ holds for this region. By this condition $G' \approx G_0$. In this case the density of the space network can be assessed from acoustic measurements by means of Eqn.(5) and (6). The values of ν calculated from acoustic measurements for the region of the rubbery state plateau are in accordance with the values ν found by a chemical method. Thus in the rubberlike-plateau take place the "normal" dependence of G on ν at which G is proportional to ν . Another dependence is observed some times at $T < T_g$.

It was established that it is the "anomalous" dependence of the storage modulus on the degree of cross-linking. Such a dependence can be observed in the glassy state or in the region of transition from the glassy to the rubbery state. In this case the storage modulus will decrease with increasing network density. An anomalous dependence of G on ν was indeed discovered in cured epoxide resins [1]. These epoxide resins with content of epoxide groups: 20,79% (*ED-20*), 16,48% (*ED-16*), 8,76% (*EDL*) were cured with meta-phenylene diamine.

Fig.3 reveals that in the glassy state the resin *EDL*, in which ν was the lowest has the greatest dynamic modulus E .

In the same state, the resin *ED-20* in which ν is the greatest has the lowest value of E . The same anomalous dependence of dynamic modulus on ν was observed for many cross-linked polymers [1]. There is a temperature (some-times a temperature interval) that is a sort of "inversion point" at which the nature of the dependence of the modulus of elasticity on the cross-linkage factor changes.

Numerous experimental values show that G epoxide matrices changes with temperature from 10MPa in rubber-like plateau to $\sim 3GPa$ at low temperatures. For example the matrix *EDT-10* ($M_c = 389$) has in rubber-like plateau $G_0 = 33MPa$, for the resin *EDT-10* ($M_c = 833$) modifying by Diethylene Glycol $G_0 = 16MPa$ and for the epoxide matrix *UP-610* $G_0 = 21MPa$. At temperature 293K we have some anomaly: for *EDT-10* $G' = 1GPa$, for *EDT-10* with *DEG* $G' = 1GPa$ and for *UP-610* $G' = 1,4GPa$. At more low temperatures (at $T \rightarrow 0$) the epoxide matrices exhibit tendency to the equalization of the value G . For example at 77K the resin *EDT-10* has $G = 2,7GPa$, but two others epoxide resins have the equals values $G = 3,1GPa$. It was found that the value G of the majority of epoxide matrices aspires to some common limit. By the linear extrapolation of the dependences $G' = f(T)$ to 4,2K it was found that $G = 3,2GPa$. It is interesting that the values G of epoxide resin calculated from ultrasonic measurements at 4,2K lead also to

$G_{\infty} = 3,2 \text{ GPa}$ [5]. Obviously at so low temperature for the epoxide resins the condition $\omega\tau \gg 1$ is valid. With this condition the first term on the right-hand side of Eqn.(5) is negligibly small compared with second term and Eqn.(5) can be written in the following form:

$$G' = G_{\infty} = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} H(\tau) d(\ln \tau) \quad (7)$$

The independence G_{∞} of the chemical structure and the frequency caused them that all epoxide resins at these conditions have approximately equal relaxation spectrum.

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